

The advantages of networks and alliances for the third space

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This session was an exploration of what kind of networks are active in supra-regional and regional contexts in the field of instructional design/eLearning, specifically on LMSs such as Moodle but also in other areas of the third space, and how we get involved and help each other. The questions for the Third Space Symposium (3SS) were based on experiences gained from collaboration in various networks in German-speaking countries, in which employees from the third space come together to work on topics related to technology-enhanced learning. In the 3SS the attendees discussed and collected their networks and explained to each other how they benefited from them, including not only well-known associations like, for example, ASCILITE, but also informal or less-known networks. The results of the discussions were that participants were inspired to become active in a network or learned how to join an alliance.

Provocation

What kind of networks are active in supra-regional and regional contexts in the field of instructional design/eLearning, or specifically on LMS such as Moodle or in other areas of the third space?

Reflection

The discussion in the 3SS led to filling a world map with the networks mentioned and structuring them into different categories.

We considered the features of professional networks that have a formal structure and a wide, supra-regional reach, such as ASCILITE or the German-registered association Moodle an Hochschulen e.V., which hold conferences and webinars and are supported by an advisory board. The German Moodle association is one example of the networks that are active in the third space which are interested in promoting one specific digital tool: the association also uses Moodle as a virtual platform for the exchange of knowledge and mutual support. There is not only this supra-regional wide organization which is financed by its members but also the regional project Moodle.NRW funded by the government of the German county North Rhein–Westphalia. Both networks support each other and are engaged in the global Moodle community.

Other networks, on the other hand, deal with specific technology-enhanced teaching methods, for example ePortfolios Australia or the several German-speaking networks focusing on E-Assessment and E-examination didactics. In the author's region, the state's Ministry of Science promotes cooperative projects between more than 30 state-run applied science universities, universities, and art and music colleges. Those activities enable different people from the third space to work together and present their results at conferences.

This selection raises the question of what specific added value regional, supra-regional and global contacts offer for knowledge exchange and how easy they are to find and access. The TELedvisors Network, a special interest group of ASCILITE, takes a particularly inviting approach, appealing to educational advisors from the technology-supported field of learning and teaching to join this community of practice. The network is international and covers a wide range of topics from professional practice, such as teaching and learning, LMS, research projects, and important exchanges on professional development.

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